

CHARACTERISTICS OF IMPROVING COMMUNICATION AND METHODOLOGICAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article focuses on the communicative-methodological competence of future foreign language teachers to teach a particular foreign language and implement it as a teacher's competence. In this context, methodological competence serves as the most important component of a communicative competence of a foreign language teacher.*

Keywords: *pedagogical conditions, communicative competence, pedagogical features, component.*

The modern characteristics of the teacher's practical pedagogical activity emphasize the practical orientation of his thinking. Practical orientation implies the implementation of creative efforts to design the learning process and model communicative communication. It also includes the logical analysis of educational material, the structure of its information structure, the integration of interdisciplinary links, the definition of the verbal structure of educational information, the development of active and independent learning activities, finding optimal combinations of reproductive and creative activities. .

It follows from this characteristic that methodical thinking as a type of pedagogical thinking is related to pedagogical consciousness and is its most important component. That is, the implementation of research, design-constructive and practical pedagogical activities, which differ in goals, means and results, is regulated by methodological thinking [1; p.12].

According to I.P. Andriadi, one of the most difficult tasks is the formation of methodological competence in FL teachers due to the diversity of approaches to teaching FL and the specificity of the subject taught. The author points out that the methodological competence of practicing teachers and the real level of professional competence in general are insufficient. Most graduates apply only partially the knowledge acquired in higher education institutions and are not always able to put theoretical material into practice. At the same time, they do not seek to acquaint themselves with new scientific developments, considering the specialized literature to be overly theoretical. According to the author, the problem is often related to insufficient methodological competence, and young teachers (and even experienced teachers) lose themselves in the flow of information, in a variety of textbooks and approaches [2; p.26].

According to A.V. Khodikina's dissertation research, methodological competence is a specific characteristic of a subject that includes cognitive, motivational, value, and practical aspects / aspects that are manifested in the implementation of successful actions in a particular field[3; p. 165].

In the process of education, the development of methodological competencies, characterized by a set of professional skills (motivational, cognitive, diagnostic, design, organizational, linguistic, creative and reflexive skills) was identified. Cognitive skills of the curriculum based on knowledge of special and general disciplines are noteworthy.

So, after listening to a course of lectures on foreign language teaching methods, active participation in seminars, the future foreign language teacher:

- Must have an understanding of:
 - The laws of the methodology of teaching foreign languages as a science and its relationship with related disciplines:
 - must know:
 - modern approaches to the process of teaching foreign languages;
 - basic concepts and categories of foreign language teaching methods;
 - Objectives, content and principles of foreign language teaching;
 - Methods of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan and abroad;
 - to be able to use the main components of the Educational-Methodical Complex on foreign languages and taking into account the specific educational conditions;
 - modern technologies of foreign language teaching;
 - The main ways to get acquainted with the language material and ways to strengthen it at different stages of teaching;
 - Features of oral and written communication and the conditions and laws of its formation at different stages of teaching;
 - must be able to:
 - select and use different teaching aids in accordance with the goals and objectives of the educational process; analysis of educational-methodical complex;
 - development of pronunciation, lexical, grammatical skills;
 - use different exercises to develop communicative competence at different stages of learning;
 - use of techniques for activating communication in a foreign language in the learning process;
 - organization of independent work of students in the classroom and outside the school;
 - take notes on all types of speech activities;
 - must have:
 - technology of teaching speech skills (listening comprehension, speaking, reading, writing).

Thus, during the study, the scientist A.V. Khodikina concludes that methodological competence is one of the key components of a bachelor of pedagogy's professional competence in foreign languages. Expressions of complex human characteristics ean. methodological competence includes fundamental and specific knowledge, plural skills, personal and professional qualities, and is associated with other competencies. That is, the methodological skills of a foreign language teacher based on linguistic, pedagogical and psychological knowledge and skills and reinforced by all other disciplines with a mandatory professional orientation are a factor in developing the system of professional training [3; p. 45-51].

In a number of studies, methodological skill is defined as a special type of professional pedagogical competence in the field of methodology, which is defined as an integral multi-level professional feature of the individual, communication and professional activity, which is equated with other types of psychological and pedagogical competence, pedagogical culture. studied.

Methodological competence is defined by the scientist A.V. Malev as "... the use of language for professional purposes, language knowledge, language skills, the acquisition of such professional skills related to the main functions of a foreign language teacher" [4; p.65]. According to the author's own research, the formation of methodological competence in pedagogical higher

education institutions implies a whole set of knowledge in the field of didactics, psychology, linguistics and psycholinguistics, integrated into the methodology. According to the author, the preparation of the bachelor should be focused on the development of constructive, projective and heuristic competencies that allow students to organize their activities in the classroom and manage these activities. In the process of teaching, the bachelor must master the competence of teaching a foreign language, the competence of speech development and the competence of developing speech activity in FL.

Scientist A.V. Malev includes in the structure and content of methodical competencies such constructive-methodical, project-methodical and methodical-heuristic competencies, as well as competencies such as language (s) teaching competencies, speech development competencies and speech activity development competencies in FL [4; p.62-65].

In the development of communicative competence E.G.Azimov and Leading Methodist scholars such as A.N. Shukin[5; p.115] recommend considering its units:

- 1) areas of communicative and methodological activities;
- 2) topics, communication situations and programs for their implementation / expansion;
- 3) communicative and methodological roles (positions) of interlocutors (students and educators);
- 4) types of narrations (texts) and rules of their construction;
- 5) language minimums and communicative speech actions / actions;
- 6) personal strategy of behavior in different situations of communication and interaction.

Analysis of the literature All researchers of the problem of professional competence in the field of pedagogy in general, and in particular in the field of foreign languages, distinguish between methodological or science-methodological and psychological-pedagogical competencies.

Thus, the methodological competence of a foreign language teacher implies a set of knowledge, skills and abilities of a professional and methodological nature that help students to teach a foreign language most successfully in certain specific conditions and in accordance with the established goals. At the same time, methodological skills are the most important component of competence.

Thus, the concept of methodological competence can be considered as one of the components of communicative competence within pedagogical communicative competence. At the same time, methodological competence is a complex interaction between the learner and the educator, reflecting the essence of pedagogical communication, which consists of the unity of the process of knowledge and communication.

The methodological competence of a teacher has its own basic basis, as it cannot exist in isolation from the subject being taught. Methodological competence implies the teaching of a particular foreign language and is implemented in it as the competence of the teacher. In this context, methodological competence serves as the most important component of a communicative competence of a foreign language teacher. Communicative competence is understood as "the ability to solve communication problems relevant to students in everyday, educational, industrial and cultural life through a foreign language; the ability of the student to use language and speech facts to achieve communication goals" [5; p. 96]. In our work we use the concept of communicative-methodical competence in this sense.

In studying the conditions of formation of communicative-methodical competence in future teachers, it is necessary to take into account the specific functions of a foreign language

teacher. For many years, the Professiogram of a Foreign Language Teacher has served as a target for teachers as a result of their educational activities, both for themselves and for the higher education institution. [4;p.112] In this "Professiogram" the following pedagogical functions of the FL teacher are distinguished:

1. constructive-planning (skills of selection and scientific organization of educational material, skills of lesson planning, etc.)
2. organizational function (organization of communication, attention to activity, etc.);
3. communicative-teaching (teaching) function (teaching in a foreign language, reconstruction of one's speech according to specific teaching conditions);
4. research (gnostic) function (ability to identify individual and age characteristics of others, the ability to analyze the process and results of their activities, etc.) [4; p.15].

These features of foreign language teacher activity were formed long before the introduction of the competency-based approach, but they have not lost their relevance for today's teaching practice.

Researcher A.S. Karpov identifies the following qualifications of an FL teacher:

- cognitive skills - skills related to the organization of attention and the development of its: general observation, flexibility, stability, selectiveness (selectivity) and other features; this includes social perception skills - noticing and interpreting signals in learners attitudes towards their own state, mood, etc .

- Socio-communicative skills: communication skills with the audience: the ability to understand how to demonstrate communicative activity through speech, facial expressions, gestures; the ability to engage the interlocutor in communication, to regulate the nature of communication, etc .;

- socio-psychological skills: the ability to "use all available energy (ability)", the ability to create and maintain their own image, the most effective in terms of influence, the ability to personalize speech;

- Organizational skills: to organize the work of the class in the right direction, to organize their activities by distributing and providing the maximum acceptance of educational material.

Scholar L.S. Karpov proposes to understand the professionally important skills of a teacher, first of all, as the ability to organize teaching activities in a pedagogically and psychologically correct way [6; p.53].

Well-known scientist E.I. Passov highlights the following professionally important skills of a foreign language teacher, which should be formed during their studies at the university[7; p.115]:

1. Design skills (ability to follow the purpose of the lesson (cycle); ability to follow the integrity of the lesson).
2. Adaptation skills (implementation of teaching activities in the context of emerging and changing conditions, the search for appropriate adequate approaches to achieving the goals, adapting the planned methods of teaching to the conditions of their implementation).
3. Organizational skills (ability to provide any type of work in the classroom).
4. Communicative skills (not only on the basis of information, but also the ability of students to communicate on the basis of auditory (voice, pauses, external noises) and visual (facial expressions, hand gestures, poses) channels (paralinguistic and extralinguistic components).
5. Motivational skills (the ability to demonstrate the importance of science, the interest of

students through the process of acquiring a foreign language culture, the involvement of all students in work, encouragement of independent work).

6. Skills of control and self-control (determination of the nature of control, separation of objects of control from the learning process, drawing correct conclusions); research skills (analytical skills, research skills, generalization and application of scientific knowledge).

Hence, in the methodological literature, most research scholars point out the need to cultivate a set of methodological skills in a foreign language teacher.

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